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Study on the Role of Training Delivery and Methodology in HR Practices in the IT Sector in Bengaluru

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ABSTRACT

This research looks at how training delivery and methods impact HR practices in the Indian IT sector. It reviews commonly used training approaches, assesses their effectiveness, and points out existing gaps and challenges. The study uses a mixed-method design, collecting data from HR professionals and employees through surveys and interviews. Findings show that while digital training methods have improved reach and flexibility, there is still room for growth in personalization and interactivity. The research offers practical insights for organizations to connect training with strategic HR goals and improve overall workforce skills.

Keywords: *Training delivery, HR practice, IT sector, methodology, employee performance.*

Introduction

The Indian IT sector is one of the most dynamic and quickly changing industries in the world. It relies heavily on skilled workers. How training is delivered and the methods used are crucial for improving employee capabilities, meeting organizational goals, and remaining competitive. This study looks into how training practices fit into HR functions and how effective they are in promoting employee growth, performance, and retention.

Objectives of research

- To look at the different training delivery methods used in the Indian IT sector.
- To understand how training methods fit into HR practices.
- To assess how effective training programs are for employee performance and motivation.
- To find the challenges HR faces when implementing training programs.
- To recommend ways to improve training strategies for better HR effectiveness

Review of Literature

Kim Buch et.al 2002 Learning style and training delivery mode preference Learning styles affect training preferences. However, classroom training is still the most favored method for adult learners.

Elizabeth M Hodge, et.al 2004 Student perceptions of course delivery methods the study found that students liked teaching methods that catered to different learning styles, promoted active engagement, and included interaction with instructors. This shows the need for a mixed-method approach based on the Seven Principles for Good Practice.

Russell F. Korte, et.al 2006 Variations Affecting Delivery where the structured training helps with planning. However, its rigidity can limit adaptability. This highlights the need for flexible, interactive methods that balance formal and informal learning to improve effectiveness.

Ajaz Akbar, et.al 2010 The training and development are crucial for organizational success. It highlights employee feedback from SBI and J&K Bank. It identifies key areas for improvement, such as trainer effectiveness, methods, environment, and facilities.

Stephen Manloney, et.al 2011 Web-Based Versus Face- To-Face Delivery of Education in Prescription of Falls-Prevention Exercise to Health Professionals found that online and in-person training was equally effective for exercise prescription in fall prevention. This suggests that practical factors, such as accessibility, should influence the choice of delivery method.

Julia Bluestone, et.al 2013 Evidence from an integrative literature review using effective teaching methods with the right settings, frequency, and media can improve learning. This approach may also enhance clinical practices, particularly when using well-evaluated, culturally relevant strategies in low- and middle-income countries.

Susan M Breitenstein, et.al 2014 The digital parent training was somewhat effective in improving outcomes for both children and parents. It provided greater reach and sustainability. However, it also emphasized the need for more research on standardizing dosage and comparing methods.

Nayef Abdulla Al-Anezi, et.al 2015 The paper highlights KOC's organized training approach, which focuses on Instructor Led and on the job Training. It connects with business goals through planning, evaluation, and assessment. It also emphasizes the need for leadership-driven cultural change to support continuous learning

Mohammed S Hashem M, et.al 2019 There is no major differences in knowledge retention among the four confined space safety training methods. It highlighted that factors related to the learner, such as industry experience and long-term retention, are more important than the delivery method.

Roya Raesinafchi, et.al 2025 It will impact on learning outcomes and engagement among construction workers the learner is centered and balanced training methods improved worker engagement and hazard recognition. However, risk tolerance did not change. The safety training should match specific goals and available resources.

Research Gap

Citation	Design of Research	Objective of Research	Key Findings	Identified Research Gap
Kim Buch et al. (2002)	Exploratory study with 165 employees	To examine the link between learning styles and training delivery mode preference	Convergers preferred computer-based; Assimilators preferred print; classroom most preferred overall	Lack of industry- specific analysis and scalability across sectors
Elizabeth M. Hodge et al. (2004)	Survey-based perception analysis	To explore student perceptions of online, traditional, and blended course delivery	Students favored active and diverse methods; interaction enhanced learning	Limited to student context; lacks employee training environment validation
Russell F. Korte et al. (2006)	Conceptual and reflective paper on implementation Phase	To address the failure of rigid training systems in dynamic environments	Implementation must be adaptive and flexible	No empirical validation; needs case- based or sectoral testing
Ajaz Akbar et al. (2010)	Empirical study on SBI and J&K Bank employees	To assess effectiveness of training delivery and methods in banking	Gaps found in trainer competence, methods, and facilities	Lacks comparative analysis with private banks or modern training formats
Stephen Manloney et al. (2011)	Experimental comparison between web- based and F2F education	To compare digital vs. face- to-face delivery for fall- prevention education	Both equally effective; web delivery better for access	Focused only on health professionals; needs replication in corporate Settings
Julia Bluestone et al. (2013)	Integrative literature review	To analyze effective training designs for health workers	Practice- relevant, repetitive, realistic settings improve outcomes	Lack of experimental data; regional differences not evaluated
Susan M. Breitenstein et al. (2014)	Systematic review of 11 studies	To evaluate digital parenting training methods	Moderate behavioral effects; varied completion rates	Does not compare digital vs. traditional methods directly; lacks longitudinal Data
Nayef Al- Anezi et al. (2015)	Case study of Kuwait Oil Company	To present a successful integrated training	Instructor-led + OJT with evaluation ensures	Not generalizable; lacks comparison with non-oil sectors or e- learning

		delivery model	training effectiveness	Systems
Mohammed S. Hashem M. et al. (2019)	Experimental study in construction safety training	To evaluate how delivery methods affect safety knowledge retention	No significant difference in method; learner experience mattered more	Lacks evaluation of blended or hybrid methods and long-term impact
Roya Raeisinafchi et al. (2025)	Comparative evaluation of five delivery methods	To measure training impact on hazard recognition and engagement	Learner-centered formats improved engagement and Recognition	Risk tolerance unchanged; limited impact evaluation over Time

Table 01: Research Gap**Figure 01 The Role on Training delivery**

- **Problem statement**

Training programs struggle to make a real impact because they rely on outdated delivery styles and rigid methods. When training did not match their needs or learning styles learners will feel difficult

- Learner may face challenges like limited time access to technology, unclear content and effective training
- Sessions are often boring or too fast, making it hard for people to stay focused or learn properly
- learners will face lack of time, poor internet and confusing content
- trainers may not be well prepared which may affect how the training is delivered

Adopting flexible and regular feedback can bridge the gap between learners and real world, however training will become more powerful tool for personal and professional growth.

Research Methodology

- **Research Design**

This study uses a descriptive exploratory design which aimed to describe current training practices and explore what could be improved and to understand how training is delivered and how different methods impact the learning. A mixed methods approach is chosen to gather both measurable data through surveys.

- **Quantitative method**

Along with survey close ended questions were used to collect structured data from a larger group of participants, identify trends in training preferences, satisfaction and delivery effectiveness

- **Qualitative method**

Interviews and open-ended questions were asked to gather personal experiences and opinion and challenges related to training methods and adding depth and context is used to collect.

- **Primary Data**

Primary data was collected directly from individuals and various training programs which include real time feedback based on their personal Learning experiences such as surveys, interviews, observations and primary data is collected through a structure questionnaire.

- **Secondary data**

Secondary data is gathered from academic journals, industry reports, data bases and published articles related to training delivery and methodology sources such as Harvard business review Mc Kinsey reports, and research papers from Google scholar are referred Sampling Technique

- **Sampling Technique**

Participants were chosen based on their availability and recent experience with training programs to reach people who can easily share honest feedback, whether they attended in person or through online training sessions

- **Sample Size**

5 companies were included from Bangalore 97 employees responded to the survey

- **Data collection method**

Primary data: collected through a st questionnaires Question type: close ended (Likert scale: strongly agree to strongly disagree)

- **Data analysis techniques**

Used descriptive statistics to summarize responses (percentages, pie charts)

Analysis and Discussion

Figure 02 Education qualification

Bachelor degree	63.9%
Diploma	19.6%
Master's Degree	15.5%
Uneducated	1%
Total	100%

Table 01: Responses

- **Interpretation**

Most participants have bachelor's degrees, which positions them well to benefit from structured training programs. The range of education levels suggests that training should be adaptable and inclusive, catering to different understanding levels.

Figure 03 Training programs in the organization from past 12 months

• Interpretation

This high participation rate shows a strong training culture in the organization. It suggests that the organization values continuous learning and invests in developing its workforce 80.4% of employees confirmed they attended formal training programs in the last 12 months. Only 11.3% said they did not, and 8.2% were unsure.

Figure 04 Type of training delivery method used most frequently

Classroom/instructor-led training	61.5%
Online/virtual	21.9%
On-the-job training	9.4%
Blended (mix of online & offline)	7.3%
Total	100%

Table 02: Responses

Interpretation

Classroom/instructor-led training remains the most preferred method, likely due to its structured format and interactive environment. However, the significant percentage of online training shows a shift toward digital learning, possibly influenced by changes after the pandemic.

Figure05 Training methodology most effective

Case Study	66.7%
Role Plays	21.9%
Group Discussion	9.4%
Hands-on Practice	2%
Total	100%

Table 03: Responses

Interpretation

Case studies are seen as very effective, probably because they help apply learning to real-life scenarios and improve critical thinking and decision-making skills. Role plays come next, especially beneficial for developing communication and behavioral skills. The low selection of hands-on practice may reflect limited opportunities within the training sessions

Figure 06 Training Materials Used

Agree	53.6%
Strongly Agree	6.2%
Disagree	18.6%
Strongly Disagree	21.6%
Total	100%

Table 04: Responses

Interpretation

While most participants find the materials useful, a total of 40.2% disagreed or strongly disagreed. This indicates room for improvement in training content, which may be outdated, too general, or not relevant to job roles, or perhaps delivered poorly.

Figure 07 Primary objective of the training

Skill Development	63.9%
Policy Training	22.7%
Leadership	7.2%
Role-specific Knowledge	6.2%
Total	100%

Table 05: Responses

Interpretation

The main goal is skill development, which aligns with the need in the industry to upgrade both technical and soft skills. However, the low focus on leadership and role-specific knowledge may point to a gap in succession planning or specialized training paths.

Conclusion, Limitations, Implications & Future Recommendation:

Conclusion

The study highlights the important role that training delivery and methodology play in improving HR practices within the Indian IT sector. Effective training not only boosts technical and soft skills among employees but also increases employee engagement, job satisfaction, and organizational productivity. The findings show that while digital platforms like LMS, webinars, and virtual labs dominate the training landscape, blended learning approaches that mix in-person and online training produce better results in learning retention and performance improvement.

Additionally, the connection between training and broader HR functions, such as performance appraisal, career development, and employee retention, is still evolving. Many organizations are moving towards data-driven training decisions, but there is still a gap in systematically evaluating training effectiveness.

Limitations of the Study

The number of participants is limited, in which may affect how widely the results will be applied. Training was conducted over a short period and have measured for long term impact where compared to different training approaches which have been influenced the learning experience and different trainers brought different styles in a each sessions in a small group of people involved so that the results might not reflect everyone's experience

Implications of the Study

The training will be flexible enough to meet everyone's needs and people will learn in different ways A good trainer makes a big difference in a very possible way to explain and connect with people Training feels more fun and interactive when people are more interested to learn more The training is all about learning and using skills in a better way In future trying out different training approaches which help to find who truly works best for different groups

Future Recommendations

Ask for honest feedback after each session to improve future training keep the content updated and fresh often so it stays relevant to today's challenges and tools support the trainers to be confident and to be prepared and learn the new experience which take time to really understand, who you are training and their background, comfort level and how they learn best keeping the sessions simple, clear, and spaced out, so people can absorb the information without feeling rushed

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